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ABSTRACT BOOK

Posters

Ilizarov Technique in Treatment of Acute Humeral Fractures And Humeral Shaft Nonunions

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SUMMARY

Introduction. Treatment methods for multiple fractures of the humerus and humeral shaft nonunions have not yet been uniformly adopted anywhere in the world.

Methods. A total of 54 patients with different types of fractures and nonunions of the humerus were treated. Of that number, 24 of them (44%) had acute fractures. A total of 30 nonunion fractures (56%) were treated. In the work, we used the methods of clinical follow-up, standard radiographs, CT scan, Stewart-Hundley functional scale after treatment of humeral fracture, and DASH-scoring system after treatment of humeral shaft nonunion.

Results. In the treatment of acute fractures, we had complete healing in 22 patients (91.6%). We had prolonged sanation in 2 patients (8.4%). In the presentation of the functional results, we used the Stewart-Hundley scale and according to it, we had 17 excellent, 5 good, and 2 bad results. The results after the treatment of non-union fractures of the humerus were: we recorded complete healing in 27 (90%) cases, while in 3 (10%) cases, non-union occurred. In those three cases, the appliance was re-adjusted, where there were two complete fusions and in one it was not due to wearing intolerance. The mean DASC score was 22.1.

Conclusion. Good functional and bony results, minimization of the risk of infection, and great stability of the device give this method a valid place in the treatment of acute fractures and humeral shaft non-union.

Keywords: Transosseous osteosynthesis; Ilizarov technique; acute humeral fractures; nonunion of the humerus